

OPERATION PROCESS IN AN ASYMMETRIC TWO-ROLL MODULE

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Abstract: The study is devoted to the analysis of the condition of capture in a two-roll module. A two-roll module is considered, in which the rolls are located relative to the vertical with a tilt to the right, the lower roll is a driven one, the roll diameters are unequal, the rolls have elastic coatings of different stiffness (so, the friction coefficients of the rolls are not equal over the material layer), the material layer is tilted downwards. It was found that the sum of the contact angles and the sum of the capture angles does not depend on the tilt of feeding the layer of material to the line of centers and on the tilt of the upper roll relative to the vertical. It has been established that the conditions for the capture of a layer of material by a pair of rolls with elastic coatings are determined by the radii of the rolls, the distance between the rolls and the coefficients of friction of the rolls over the material layer.

1. Introduction

The tasks of contact interaction in the two-roll modules of technological machines are very complex and long ago have attracted the attention of researchers.

The variety of machine assignments, the difference in the requirements for their parameters, the difference in the properties of the material being processed led to the appearance of a large number of studies [1-10] devoted to the analysis of contact interaction in two-roll modules. However, the results of these studies have not yet become the basis for the theory, explaining the experiments and allowing to predict the interaction indicators in the two-roll modules.

Currently there are a lot of papers [11], devoted to theoretical analysis of the condition of capture in a symmetric two-roll module. There are papers [12-17], in which one or several types of asymmetry are studied in the two-roll modules. However, at present, an integrated approach that simultaneously takes into account all possible types of asymmetry in analyzing the condition of capture in a two-roll module is absent.

In order to further develop the theoretical concepts, we have investigated the capture condition in an essentially asymmetric two-roll module. Processes in which more than two types of asymmetry are simultaneously realized are called essentially asymmetric ones [14].

The angles of contact of two-roll modules depend on the type and location of the guiding movable roller, which is designed mainly according to two schemes [18]:

1. The guide of the movable roller is a slider that moves with the roller along the guide relative to the bed frame;
2. The guide of the movable roller is a lever that connects the axis of the movable roller to the bed frame.

In [19-23], the angles of contact were determined in two-roll modules, where the slider of the movable roller moves along a center line.

This study is devoted to the determination and estimation of the angles of contact where the slider of the movable roller moves along the vertical line

2. Analytical solution to the problem posed

Consider a two-roll module presented in Fig. 1, with the following parameters: roll angle of tilt β ; roll radii - R_1, R_2 ; initial thickness of material layer - δ_1 ; the angle of tilt of the layer of material to the line of centers (axis O_1y') - γ_1 ; the distance between the rolls - h .

Assuming that the angles $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta$ and γ_1 are small, we can write equations (3) and (4) in a simplified form

$$R_1(\alpha_1 + \beta)^2 + R_2(\alpha_2 - \beta)^2 + \delta_1\gamma_1^2 + 2(h - \delta_1) = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha_2 - \beta = \frac{R_1}{R_2}(\alpha_1 + \beta) - \frac{\delta_1}{R_2}\gamma_1. \quad (6)$$

Substituting $(\alpha_2 - \beta)$ from equality (6) and after some transformations, equation (5) takes the form

$$R_1(R_1 + R_2)(\alpha_1 + \beta)^2 - 2R_1\delta_1\gamma_1(\alpha_1 + \beta) + \delta_1^2\gamma_1^2 + R_2\delta_1\gamma_1^2 + 2R_2(h - \delta_1) = 0.$$

Solving this quadratic equation, we get the angle α_1

$$\alpha_1 + \beta = \frac{\delta_1\gamma_1}{R_1 + R_2} + \sqrt{\frac{2R_2(\delta_1 - h)}{R_1(R_1 + R_2)} - \frac{R_2\delta_1(\delta_1 + R_1 + R_2)\gamma_1^2}{R_1(R_1 + R_2)^2}}. \quad (7)$$

or as a first approximation

$$\alpha_1 = \sqrt{\frac{2R_2(\delta_1 - h)}{R_1(R_1 + R_2)}} - \frac{(R_1 + R_2)\beta - \delta_1\gamma_1}{R_1 + R_2}. \quad (8)$$

Taking into account the expression (8) from equality (6) we find the formula for determining the angle α_2 :

$$\alpha_2 = \sqrt{\frac{2R_1(\delta_1 - h)}{R_2(R_1 + R_2)}} + \frac{(R_1 + R_2)\beta - \delta_1\gamma_1}{R_1 + R_2}. \quad (9)$$

Adding expressions (8) and (9) after transformations, we find the sum of the angles α_1 and α_2 :

$$\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 = \sqrt{\frac{2(R_1 + R_2)(\delta_1 - h)}{R_1 R_2}}. \quad (10)$$

After contact in section A_1A_2 , the layer of material or roll coating can be deformed and therefore the capture of a layer of material is not in the section A_1A_2 , but in the section $A'_1A'_2$. The capture angles α'_1 and α'_2 are less than the contact angles α_1 and α_2 .

At points A'_1 and A'_2 from the side of the rolls, the forces of normal pressure N_1, N_2 and friction forces T_1, T_2 act on the layer of material. To fulfill the capture, it is necessary that the components of the friction forces along the axis of the vertical line of centers $T_{1x'}$ and $T_{2x'}$ be greater than the components of the normal pressure forces along the axis of the vertical line of centers $N_{1x'}$ and $N_{2x'}$ or, at least, be equal to them. Mathematically, this condition is formulated as follows:

$$N_{1x'} + N_{2x'} + T_{2x'} \leq T_{1x'}. \quad (11)$$

In addition to condition (11), we construct the equilibrium equation along the axis O_1y'

$$N_{1y'} - N_{2y'} + T_{1y'} + T_{2y'} = 0. \quad (12)$$

From the scheme of forces in Fig. 1 we get

$$\begin{aligned} N_{1x'} &= N_1 \sin(\alpha'_1 + \beta), \quad T_{1x'} = T_1 \cos(\alpha'_1 + \beta), \quad N_{1y'} = N_1 \cos(\alpha'_1 + \beta), \quad T_{1y'} = T_1 \sin(\alpha'_1 + \beta), \\ N_{2x'} &= N_2 \sin(\alpha'_2 - \beta), \quad T_{2x'} = T_2 \cos(\alpha'_2 - \beta), \quad N_{2y'} = N_2 \cos(\alpha'_2 - \beta), \quad T_{2y'} = T_2 \sin(\alpha'_2 - \beta). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

With these expressions, inequality (11) and equality (12) are rewritten as

$$N_1 \sin(\alpha'_1 + \beta) - T_1 \cos(\alpha'_1 + \beta) \leq -(N_2 \sin(\alpha'_2 - \beta) + T_2 \cos(\alpha'_2 - \beta)), \quad (14)$$

$$N_1 \cos(\alpha'_1 + \beta) + T_1 \sin(\alpha'_1 + \beta) = (N_2 \cos(\alpha'_2 - \beta) - T_2 \cos(\alpha'_2 - \beta)). \quad (15)$$

The value of the friction force T_2 , can be determined from the equality [19]

$$M_m = T_m r_m = N_2 f_m r_m = T_2 R_2,$$

where M_m - is the moment created by the forces of friction in the necks of the upper free roll; T_m - is the resultant friction forces in the necks; r_m - is the neck radius; f_m - is the coefficient of friction in the neck. Hence

$$T_2 = N_2 f_m \frac{r_m}{R_2} = f'_2 N_2,$$

where $f'_2 = f_m \frac{r_m}{R_2}$ - is the coefficient of friction of a free roll over a layer of material.

According to the Amonton law of friction for the driven lower roll, we have

$$T_1 = f'_1 N_1,$$

where f'_1 - is the coefficient of friction of the driven roll over a layer of material.

Substitute the values T_1 and T_2 in inequality (14) and equality (15), we get

$$N_1 (\sin(\alpha'_1 + \beta) - f'_1 \cos(\alpha'_1 + \beta)) \leq -N_2 (\sin(\alpha'_2 - \beta) + f'_2 \cos(\alpha'_2 - \beta)), \quad (16)$$

$$N_1 (\cos(\alpha'_1 + \beta) + f'_1 \sin(\alpha'_1 + \beta)) = N_2 (\cos(\alpha'_2 - \beta) - f'_2 \cos(\alpha'_2 - \beta)). \quad (17)$$

From equality (17) we define the force N_2

$$N_2 = N_1 \frac{\cos(\alpha'_1 + \beta) + f'_1 \sin(\alpha'_1 + \beta)}{\cos(\alpha'_2 - \beta) - f'_2 \sin(\alpha'_2 - \beta)}. \quad (18)$$

Introducing the force value N_2 into the condition (16) and after a series of transformations we find

$$\operatorname{tg}(\alpha'_1 + \alpha'_2) \leq \frac{f'_1 - f'_2}{1 + f'_1 f'_2}.$$

Considering $\frac{f'_1 - f'_2}{1 + f'_1 f'_2} = \frac{\operatorname{tg} v'_1 - \operatorname{tg} v'_2}{1 + \operatorname{tg} v'_1 \operatorname{tg} v'_2}$, we get

$$\alpha'_1 + \alpha'_2 \leq v'_1 - v'_2, \quad (19)$$

where v'_1 - is the friction angle at a point A'_1 ; v'_2 - is the angle of friction of the free roll.

A similar analysis is done for capture angles α'_1, α'_2 , and their sum in section $A'_1 A'_2$ and for contact angles α_1, α_2 and their sum in section $A_1 A_2$. Then we get

$$\alpha'_1 = \sqrt{\frac{2R_2(\delta_2 - h)}{R_1(R_1 + R_2)}} - \frac{(R_1 + R_2)\beta - \delta_2 \gamma_2}{R_1 + R_2}, \quad \alpha'_2 = \sqrt{\frac{2R_1(\delta_2 - h)}{R_2(R_1 + R_2)}} + \frac{(R_1 + R_2)\beta - \delta_2 \gamma_2}{R_1 + R_2}, \quad (20)$$

$$\alpha'_1 + \alpha'_2 = \sqrt{\frac{2(R_1 + R_2)(\delta_2 - h)}{R_1 R_2}}, \quad (21)$$

where δ_2 - is the thickness of the layer of material in the cross section $A'_1 A'_2$; γ_2 - is the tilt angle of the layer of material to $O_1 y'$ axis in cross section $A'_1 A'_2$.

Find the difference $R_1 \alpha'_1 - R_2 \alpha'_2$ by the expressions (20) and (21):

$$R_1\alpha'_1 - R_2\alpha'_2 = \delta_2\gamma_2 - (R_1 + R_2)\beta.$$

It has the form:

$$\gamma_2 = \frac{R_1\alpha'_1 - R_2\alpha'_2 + (R_1 + R_2)\beta}{\delta_2}. \quad (22)$$

Derive the equation of force equilibrium of the layer of material at the time of contact with the rolls:

$$\begin{cases} \sum X' = -N_{1x'} - N_{2x'} + T_{1x'} - T_{2x'} = 0, \\ \sum Y' = N_{1y'} - N_{2y'} + T_{1y'} + T_{2y'} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

Having made similar transformations in the system with inequality (11) and equality (12), we have

$$\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 = \nu_1 - \nu'_2, \quad (24)$$

where ν_1 - is the friction angle at a point A_1 ; ν'_2 - is the angle of friction of the free roll.

Let the difference between the contact angle α_1 and the capture angle α'_1 be equal to μ_1 , and between the angles α_2 and α'_2 be equal to μ_2 . Then from inequality (19) we have

$$\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 \leq \nu'_1 - \nu'_2 + \mu_1 + \mu_2 \quad (25)$$

or with equality (24)

$$\mu_1 + \mu_2 \geq \nu_1 - \nu'_1. \quad (26)$$

With some approximation we may assume that $R_1\mu_1 = R_2\mu_2$. Hence from (26) we get

$$\mu_1 \geq \frac{R_2}{R_1 + R_2}(v_1 - v'_1), \quad \mu_2 \geq \frac{R_1}{R_1 + R_2}(v_1 - v'_1).$$

Hence

$$\mu_{1\min} = \frac{R_2}{R_1 + R_2}(v_1 - v'_1), \quad \mu_{2\min} = \frac{R_1}{R_1 + R_2}(v_1 - v'_1). \quad (27)$$

From these dependencies it follows that the differences between the contact angles and the capture angles depend mainly on the radii of the rolls and the difference of the friction angles of the driven roll at the points of contact and capture.

3. Conclusion

The following aspects are considered in the paper: the conditions of capture in a two-roll module in which the rolls are located relative to the vertical with the tilt on the right, the lower roll is driven, the diameters of the rolls are not equal, the rolls have elastic coatings of various materials, the material layer is tilted downward to the line of centers.

Dependences are obtained for calculating the values of the following geometrical parameters: contact angles; capture angles; the maximum thickness of the layer of material at its capture; the angle of tilt of the layer of material to the line of centers when it is captured; the differences between contact angles and capture angles.

Analysis of the results of calculation of the obtained dependencies showed the following:

- patterns of change in the contact angle of the upper roll and the contact angle of the lower roll from the distance between the rolls and the thickness of the material layer are the same;
- the difference between the contact angles and the grip angles depends mainly on the roll radii and the difference in the friction angles of the drive roll at the contact and grip points.

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